

Practice Abstract no. 28

Food and nutrition components - Dataset creation tool

To facilitate the development of innovative applications for personalised nutrition and food retail, FOODITY has made available five components. FOODITY partner CERTH crafted these components and are directly related to functions concerning food and nutrition.

This practice abstract describes the dataset creation tool component, particularly its characteristics, specific formats, functionalities, the mechanisms in which they operate, and the licensing terms under which it can be made available.

What is provided	A dataset creation tool.
Component format	In the format of a spreadsheet (Excel).
What it does	Helps a user create a nutrition dataset.
How it works	The McCance and Widdowsons dataset ¹ is a comprehensive nutrition dataset featuring a variety of English foods. In addition to nutritional details, it also includes information on vitamins, micronutrients, macronutrients, and more. The dataset is organised into multiple interconnected Excel tabs, offering users a simple way to search for foods. By typing in the name of a food, the tool displays all relevant results. Once the desired food is found, the corresponding nutrient and vitamin information is provided.
Technical details/considerations	The above tool needs the Microsoft Office Excel program or can be used with the online Google Sheets.
Related datasets/standards	The tool uses the McCance and Widdowsons dataset which is a dataset of 3000 foods with their corresponding nutrition, vitamins, and other attributes.
References	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/composition-of-foods-integrated-dataset-cofid
IPR considerations	The component is provided under the following licence: "Food nutrition information" © 2024 by Visual Computing Laboratory (VCL) , Information Technologies Institute (ITI) , Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) is marked with CC0 1.0 .

¹ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/composition-of-foods-integrated-dataset-cofid>

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The screenshot shows a software interface for creating a dataset from a recipe. The recipe is for a 'Banana Snack Roll' and includes the following steps:

1. Spread 20-30 g of peanut butter evenly over the tortilla (50-60 g).
2. Place the banana (120-150 g) on one edge of the tortilla.
3. Roll the tortilla around the banana.
4. Slice into bite-sized pieces or enjoy as is!

The table below shows the food components extracted from the recipe:

ID	Name	Recipe (OPTIONAL)	CoFID ID	Food #1	Quantity (g/ml)	CoFID ID	Food #2	Quantity (g/ml)	CoFID ID	Food #3	Quantity (g/ml)	CoFID ID	Food #4	Quantity (g/ml)
1	Banana Snack Roll	1. Spread 20-30 g of peanut butter evenly over the tortilla (50-60 g). 2. Place the banana (120-150 g) on one edge of the tortilla. 3. Roll the tortilla around the banana. 4. Slice into bite-sized pieces or enjoy as is!	14-318	Bananas, flesh only	120	11-925	Tortilla, wheat, soft	50		Peanut butt				
2										Peanut butter, smooth				
3														
4														
5														
6														
7														
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Example of the Dataset creation tool

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